

Good practices in Do.Na.To Project communication and technical formation

Introduction

Forestry innovative projects are very important from a technical, operational and even experimental point of view, but if there is no way of transferring the knowledge and the scientific results obtained to the territory and to the supply chains, they are an end in themselves. For this reason, the importance of communication on the management of Douglas fir forests has proved to be crucial for the dissemination of knowledge and innovation in Tuscany, a region where this species has a long history of over 100 years of silviculture and still a great potential.

Within the Do.Na.To. project, Compagnia delle Foreste, a publishing company specialised in the forestry sector, was the partner in charge of communication, with the aim of reaching as many stakeholders as possible through various information products and platforms. In particular, it took care of the image of the operating group and provided information on the activities carried out and the results achieved through: website, newsletters, brochures, interviews and videos.

The Accademia dei Gergofili also organised three conferences to promote the initial, intermediate and final results of the project, with publication of the proceedings attended by academics, researchers and forest managers on the themes of: The role of Douglas-fir in climate change mitigation and adaptation; Future perspectives for Douglas-fir cultivation in Tuscany; Valorisation of Tuscan Douglas-fir wood products; Revitalisation of the Tuscan regional nursery for the production of quality seedlings; Historical Vallombrosa stands contribution to the Do.Na.To. project; Demonstration areas for natural regeneration of Douglas-fi. In addition, in order to stimulate knowledge acquisition within the partnership, a series of guided tours were organised in Germany to show demonstration sites to stakeholders with the aim of learning new knowledge about Douglas fir management and exchanging views with experts from other European countries.

This was very important to visualise the medium to long term effects of the silvicultural protocols applied and to obtain detailed information on the possible impacts of Douglas fir management.

Lessons learned

The contacts and experience gained by the partners are an important asset, as are some communication products that, by highlighting the potential of the species and the know-how acquired, will be able to publicise the results of Do.Na.To. and the experts who contributed to it, even after the project has ended. Good communication is certainly useful for involving partners and stakeholders. The project was successful and had a very structured communication strategy, which gives it a good chance of being replicated in other Italian and Mediterranean contexts.

For further information contact

David Pozzi, Project manager, Italy, e-mail: davidpozzi@agro-dendrostudio.it

Sabrina Raddi, Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: sabrina.raddi@unifi.it

Francesca Giannetti, Assistant Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: francesca.giannetti@unifi.it

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.progettodonato.it/>

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